

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH PAREMIA WITH A COMPONENT OF ZOONYMS

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Abstract. This article will consider the problem of similarities and differences between phraseological units such as paremia of zoonyms in English and Russian, based on the criteria of "moral qualities".

Paremiyas and stable expressions are an inorganic component of language culture and interpersonal communication, an important feature in terms of the national characteristics of the language under study and at the same time socio-cultural phenomena common to all peoples. Therefore, when learning a foreign language, students should pay attention to mastering this component of foreign language culture, which gives the language a special color and national flavor. The correct use of paremiological units for students in the practical application of the acquired knowledge gives this knowledge a special depth and versatility. A comparative analysis of the paremiological units of the studied foreign and native languages is also useful, which helps not only to expand the student's worldview, but also to better consolidate the material.

The purpose of the work is a comparative analysis of Russian and English paremia with zoonyms.

Keywords: paremia, proverbs, paremiology, phraseological unit, zoonym, moral qualities.

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РУССКИХ И АНГЛИЙСКИХ ПАРЕМИЙ С КОМПОНЕНТОМ ЗООНИМОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье будет рассмотрена проблема сходства и различия таких фразеологизмов, как паремия зоонимов в английском и русском языках, исходя из критериев «нравственных качеств».

Паремии и устойчивые выражения представляют собой неорганический компонент языковой культуры и межличностного общения, важный признак с точки зрения национальных особенностей изучаемого языка и в то же время общие для всех народов социокультурные явления. Поэтому при изучении иностранного языка учащиеся должны обратить внимание на овладение этим компонентом иноязычной культуры, придающим языку особый колорит и национальный колорит. Правильное использование учащимися паремиологических единиц при практическом применении полученных знаний придает этим знаниям особую глубину и многогранность. Также полезен сравнительный анализ паремиологических единиц изучаемого иностранного и родного языков, который помогает не только расширить мировоззрение учащегося, но и лучше закрепить материал.

Цель работы – сравнительный анализ русских и английских паремий с зоонимами.

Ключевые слова: паремия, пословицы, паремиология, фразеологизм, зооним, нравственные качества.

Language is the most important means of communication between people, a weapon for transmitting thoughts to others. Language is also a mirror of national culture, a treasure that preserves it. The nature of the habitat of each people, reflecting the economic system of the people, oral creativity, fiction, art, Science, traditions, accumulation and transmission from generation to generation are the national-cultural semantics of the language. National-cultural semantics is present in all layers of the language: in vocabulary, grammar, and even in phonetics. But the national-cultural semantics is very clearly manifested in the existing linguistic units. Such language units are words, phraseological units and parameters. Each language has its own vocabulary, phraseology, as well as paremiology

According to Bulach E. A. the study of the problem of paremiological constants in English and Russian phraseology covers a number of basic concepts. One of the most basic is the Macropole Man, which is represented by a large number of paremias, which together form a "paremiological portrait" of a person, are represented by the following criteria: moral qualities, existence, social sphere, appearance, emotional and mental states, labor activity, behavior, physical characteristics, mental abilities, moral and ethical ideas, speech, individuality.

Comparing Russian and English paremias with the component of zoonyms according to the criterion of "moral qualities". F. P. Wilson's Dictionary of Oxford proverbs and W. I. Based on the dictionary of Proverbs of the Russian people of Dahl, paremias were divided by zoonyms into the following components:

- 1) caution
- 2) courage, perseverance
- 3) greed
- 4) arrogance, pride
- 5) negligence
- 6) negligence, negligence
- 7) cowardice
- 8) hypocrisy, betrayal
- 9) hostility
- 10) interest
- 11) cunning, flattery
- 12) tenderness
- 13) annoyance

For comparison, it was studied on the basis of a table that reflects the differences and similarities of of paremias to the zoonyms component in Russian and English.

№	Constituting	English	Russian
1	Caution	It's a bold mouse that nestles in the cat's ear. The mouse that has taken refuge in the cat's ear is very self-confident The scalded cat fears cold water.	Не клади волку пальца в рот. Пуганная ворона куста боится.

		<p>A burnt cat is afraid of cold water.</p> <p>Send not a cat for lard.</p> <p>Do not send a cat for lard</p>	<p>Пустили козла в огород, а волк в пастухи нанялся.</p>
2	Courage, determination	<p>To beard the lion in his den. – Attacking the lion at its home .</p> <p>The bull must be taken by the horns. . Hold the bull by the horns.</p> <p>Don't make yourself a mouse, or the cat will eat you. - Don't be a mouse so the cat doesn't eat you.</p>	<p>Нужна смелость орла, чтобы разбить врага.</p> <p>Кто смел, тот и на коня сел.</p> <p>Бери быка за рога.</p> <p>Не будь овцой, так и волк не съест.</p>
3	Greed	<p>A dog in the manger. - The dog in the manger.</p> <p>Too much pudding will choke the dog. - A very large portion of pudding will strangle the dog.</p> <p>Dogs that put up many hares kill none. - Dogs that scare away many rabbits do not catch any of them.</p> <p>He that will steal an egg will steal an ox. – Whoever steals the eggs also steals the bull.</p>	<p>Собака на сене. И сам не дам, и другим не дам.</p> <p>За двумя зайцами погонишься — ни одного не поймаешь.</p> <p>Любит птичку, чтобы пела, да не ела.</p>
4	Arrogance, pride	<p>Every dog is a lion at home. - Every dog in his house is a lion.</p> <p>Don't ride a high horse. - - Do not sit on a high horse.</p> <p>A donkey in a lion's skin. An ass in lion's skin.</p>	<p>Всяк кулик на своем болоте велик.</p> <p>Осел в львиной шкуре.</p> <p>Всякая жаба себя хвалит.</p>
5	Impudence	<p>All lay load son a willing horse. – All cargo is loaded on a</p>	<p>Охочая лошадка всю поклажу везет. Кто везет,</p>

		<p>conscientious horse.</p> <p>Barking dogs seldom bite. Dogs that bark at a distance don't bark at hand. - Barking dogs rarely bite.</p>	<p>ТОГО И ПОГОНЯЮТ.</p>
6	Light-mindedness, unconcern	<p>Never buy a pig in a poke. - Never buy a pig in a bag</p> <p>.When the fox preaches, take care of your geese. - When the Fox is preaching, take care of your geese</p>	<p>Не покупай kota в мешке.</p> <p>Петуха на зарез несут, а он кричит кукареку.</p> <p>Ему и беда, что с гуся вода.</p>
7	Cowardice	<p>Hares may pull dead lions by the beard.</p> <p>A dead lion can also be pulled out with a beard.by rabbits</p> <p>As brave as lion with a lamb.</p> <p>A good fellow among sheep, and a good fellow is a sheep himself.</p> <p>Rats desert (leave) a sinking ship. Rats flee from a sinking ship.</p>	<p>Мертвый пес зайца не погонит.</p> <p>Молодец среди овец, а на молодца и сам овца.</p> <p>Крысы бегут с тонущего корабля.</p>
8	Hypocrisy, deceit	<p>A wolf in sheep's clothing. A wolf in sheep's clothing.</p> <p>Cats hide their claws. – Cats hide their claws.</p> <p>With foxes we must play the fox. – With foxes, we have to be a fox.</p>	<p>Волк в овечьей шкуре.</p> <p>С волками жить – по-волчьи выть.</p>
9	Hostility	<p>To live cat-and-dog life.</p> <p>Two dogs over one bone seldom agree. - Two dogs can't share one bone.</p> <p>The great fish eat up the small. - A big fish eats a small one.</p>	<p>Жить как кошка с собакой (вечно ссориться).</p> <p>Два медведя в одной берлоге не уживутся.</p> <p>Большая рыба маленькую целиком глотает. Кто кого сможет, тот того и гложет.</p>
10	Curiosity	<p>Curiosity killed the cat.</p>	<p>Много будешь знать - скоро состаришься</p> <p>Любопытство не порок, а</p>

			большое свинство.
11	Cunning, flattery	As slippery as an eel. Slippery as an eel (i.e. dodgy).	У хитрости тараканьи ножки. Старая лиса всегда хитра.
12	Meekness.	Even a worm will turn. - Even a worm will rear up	Незлобен как голубь. Смирная овца — волку корысть. Смирного волка и телята лижут.
13	Annoyance	Flies go to the lean horse. - Flies stick to a skinny horse (i.e. all misfortunes stick to an unlucky person).	На тощее брюхо летит комар и муха.

After analyzing the table data, the following conclusion was made.

According to the four components of the criterion "moral qualities", Russian and English paremias are compatible with zoonyms:

1. Impudence -zoonym "horse";
2. Cowardice - zoonyms "rabbit", "lion", "sheep", "rat";
3. Hypocrisy - "Wolf" zoom;
4. Boring-zoonym "fly".

According to the five components of the criterion "moral qualities", Russian and English paremias are incompatible with zoonyms:

1. Attentivness-in English zoonyms are "mouse", "cat", and in Russian - "Wolf", "Crow", "goat";
2. Light-mindedness -in English, zoonyms are "pig", "fox", and in Russian - "cat", "Rooster", "goose";
3. Curiosity -in English" cat " zoonym, and in Russian there is not;
4. Cunning- the zoonym" snake "in English, in Russian - "cockroach", "Fox";
5. Meekness.– zoonym "worm" in English, in Russian - "pigeon", "sheep", "wolf".

According to the four components of the criterion "moral qualities", Russian and English paremias are partially compatible with zoonyms:

1. Courage-zoonym "bull" in English and Russian; only in English - "lion", "mouse", "cat"; only in Russian - "eagle" – "sheep", "wolf";
2. Greed-zoonym "dog" in English and Russian; only in English - "bull"; only in Russian - "rabbit", "birds";
3. Arrogance-zoonym "donkey" in English and Russian; only in English - "dog", "horse"; only in Russian – "sandpit", "frog";
4. Hostility – in English and Russian zoonyms "cat", "dog", "fish"; only in Russian - "bear".

Conclusion

During the study, theoretical materials on such concepts as "zonyms" and "paremias" were studied. It was found that zonyms are called the names of animals. Zonyms are complex linguistic units with significant information potential. Most often, zonyms are included in stable expressions – paremias (from the Greek "proverb", "parable") - this is a stable phraseological unit, which is distinguished by the integrity and didactic nature of the content.

The practical significance of the work is that information on the similarity and differences of paremias with zonyms in Russian and English is systematized and analyzed according to the criterion of "Moral qualities".

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